

Reliability, Availability Study of Vegetable Oil Industry using Cold Standby Series-Parallel System¹

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Abstract

System configurations and component/equipment failure distribution are the two main aspects taken into account when predicting system dependability, which is a crucial aspect of system design. Management and users must assess the dependability of (vegetable oil extraction) systems in order to enhance system parameters and backup units. "Oil extraction" is the process of removing oil from seeds. Edible oils are mostly derived from oil seeds. Large-scale oilseed processing plants may be found in the majority of emerging nations. On a modest scale, vegetable oil may be produced from oilseeds in a variety of methods. For instance, water-based oil extraction techniques, manual kneading techniques, hand-operated presses, ghanis, and expellers. The magnitude of the intended operation, the quantity of oilseed or financial resources available, or both may influence the technology selection. In this paper, a system is considered which contains 4 units in which 2 units are in working mode and two are in cold standby mode. This study will use mathematical techniques such as MTSF/MTBF, Markov chain, Markov process, renewal process, and others to evaluate the system and derive various dependability metrics.

Keywords

MTSF/MTBF, Markov Chain, Markov Process, Renewal Process etc. Regenerative Point, Availability, Busy Period.

Introduction

One way to create a highly reliable system with less trustworthy components is through standby redundancy. Expected cost or continuous availability functions are frequently developed for repairable systems. The majorities of standby system reliability models now in use characterize the system's states as time-dependent distributions and presume that they are independent of one another. In this chapter a system of extraction of vegetable oil is considered which contains four units in which two units are in working mode and two are in cold standby mode. Here it is assumed that system is in up-state if any 2

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units are working. The seeds go through several processing stages at the factory before the oil is extracted. Trash, dirt, sand, and metal fragments are removed from the oilseed through cleaning. It is common practice to remove the oilseed kernel's seed covering. Known as decortication, this technique guarantees a higher protein content in the oil-cake while also increasing the oil content of the raw material entering the extraction gear. After the seed has been reduced in size, it may be rolled to create flakes that are then conditioned. The seeds go through several processing stages at the factory before the oil is extracted. Trash, dirt, sand, and metal fragments are removed from the oilseed through cleaning. Frequently, the oilseed's seed coat is removed. In order to optimize the effectiveness of oil extraction, the seed is heated and frequently treated with steam during conditioning. Oil-cakes are treated with a solvent that dissolves the oil in order to extract the oil from them. To extract the crude oil, the solvent is eliminated using heat and vacuum. The three primary processes of neutralization, bleaching, and deodorization are used to refine crude oil before vegetable oil is eventually produced. In this paper, system will be analyzed to calculate the several reliability measures by using mathematical tools MTSF/MTBF, Markov chain, Markov process, renewal process etc. There are many papers given by researcher to reduce the rate of failure, and to increase the availability of the systems, studied by Barlow and Hunter (1960). R.E Barlow, LC.Hunter solves the combination of optimum preventive maintenance and minimal repair policy.. In this paper system will be analyzed to determine various reliability measures by using mathematical tools MTSF/MTBF, Markov chain etc.

Description of system and Assumption:-

- In this model, a redundant system having four units is to be considered.
- In this system a repairable system having four units P,Q,R,S are to be considered so that if any of the two units fails leads that system causing whole system to failed state.
- Initially units P&Q are considered to be in operative and other two units R & S are considered to be in standby stage.
- It is considered that the working capacity of units R&S is less than the working capacity of Units P&Q so that these standby units works in reduced capacity after the failure of unit P&Q.
- It is considered that if one of the units is fail at a time then system is in down state.
- System is considered in Up-state if one unit is working and in down state if no unit is working.
- It is considered that whenever the units fails, the priority of repair of units is taken as $P>Q>R>S$ order.
- Each unit of the system has two modes-normal operative or failed.
- Each repair improves efficiency of working of a unit.
- A single server facility is available with the system who maintain and repair the units.
- All the random variable are independent.

Notations

E:	Set of regenerative states
\bar{E} :	Set of non-regenerative states
P,Q,R,S:	Unit is in operative state and cold standby

λ :	Invariant failure rate of a unit P
$g(t), \overline{G}(t)$:	pdf and cdf of repair time of a failed unit P
α :	Invariant failure rate of a unit Q
$h(t), \overline{H}(t)$:	pdf and cdf of repair time of a unit Q
γ :	Invariant failure rate of a unit R
$k(t), \overline{K}(t)$:	pdf and cdf of failure time of a unit R.
δ :	Invariant failure rate of a unit S
$d(t), D(t)$:	pdf and cdf of failed time of a unit.
P_r :	Failed unit P under repair
Q_r :	Failed unit Q under repair
R_r :	Failed unit R under repair
S_r :	Failed unit S under repair
©	Symbol for Laplace convolution
®	Symbol for Laplace Stieltjes Convolution
○	Up-state
□	Down-state
●	Regenerative Point

The system can be in any of the following states with respect of the above symbols:

$S_0=(P, Q, R, S)$	$S_3=(P_r, Q_r, R_r, S)$
$S_1=(P_r, Q, R, S)$	$S_4=(P, Q_r, R_r, S)$
$S_2=(P, Q_r, R, S)$	$S_5=(P_r, Q_r, R_r, S)$
$S_6=(P, Q_r, R_r, S_r)$	

Transition Probabilities

The epoch of entry into states $\{S_0, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$ are regenerative states. The transition probabilities from the states S_i to S_j are given by Q_{ij} and in the states S_i denotes the transition probability from states S_i to S_j are given under

$p_{01} = \lambda / (\lambda + \alpha)$	$p_{02} = \alpha / (\lambda + \alpha)$
$p_{10} = \beta / (\alpha + \beta)$	$p_{13} = \alpha / (\alpha + \beta)$
$p_{20} = h^*(\gamma + \lambda)$	$p_{23} = \lambda(1 - h^*(\gamma + \lambda)) / (\gamma + \lambda)$
$p_{24} = \gamma(1 - h^*(\gamma + \lambda)) / (\gamma + \lambda)$	$p_{31} = h^*(\gamma + \beta)$
$p_{32} = \beta(1 - h^*(\gamma + \beta)) / (\gamma + \beta)$	$p_{35} = \gamma(1 - h^*(\gamma + \beta)) / (\gamma + \beta)$
$p_{42} = k^*(\lambda + \delta)$	$p_{45} = \lambda(1 - k^*(\lambda + \delta)) / (\lambda + \delta)$
$p_{46} = \delta(1 - k^*(\lambda + \delta)) / (\lambda + \delta)$	$p_{53} = 1$
$p_{54} = 1$	$p_{64} = 1$

It can be easily verified that

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_{01} + p_{02} &= 1 & p_{20} + p_{23} + p_{24} &= 1 \\
 p_{31} + p_{32} + p_{35} &= 1 & p_{01} + p_{02} &= 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$p_{42} + p_{45} + p_{46} = 1$$

Mean Sojourn Times

Mean Sojourn Times may be defined by

$$\mu_i = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^x P[t : 0 < t > T] dt$$

So that in steady state we have following relations

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_0 &= \lambda / (\lambda + \alpha) & \mu_1 &= 1 / (\alpha + \beta) \\ \mu_2 &= 1 - h^*(\gamma + \lambda) / (\gamma + \lambda) & \mu_3 &= 1 - h^*(\gamma + \beta) / (\gamma + \beta) \\ \mu_4 &= 1 - k^*(\lambda + \delta) / (\lambda + \delta) \end{aligned}$$

The unconditional mean time taken by the system to transit from any states S_i to S_j is mathematically given by

$$m_{ij} = \int_0^{\infty} t dQ_{ij}(t) = -Q_{ij}^*(s) \Big|_{s=0}$$

So that

$$\begin{aligned} m_{01} &= \lambda / (\lambda + \alpha)^2 & m_{31} &= -h^*(\alpha + \beta) \\ m_{02} &= \alpha / (\lambda + \alpha)^2 & m_{32} &= \beta(1 - h^*(\beta + \gamma)) / (\beta + \gamma)^2 + \beta h^*(\beta + \gamma) / (\beta + \gamma) \\ m_{10} &= \beta / (\alpha + \beta)^2 & m_{35} &= \gamma(1 - h^*(\gamma + \beta)) / (\gamma + \beta)^2 + \gamma h^*(\gamma + \beta) / (\gamma + \beta) \\ m_{13} &= \alpha / (\alpha + \beta)^2 & m_{45} &= \lambda(1 - k^*(\lambda + \delta)) / (\lambda + \delta)^2 + \lambda k^*(\lambda + \delta) / (\lambda + \delta) \\ m_{20} &= -h^*(\gamma + \lambda) & m_{46} &= \delta(1 - k^*(\lambda + \delta)) / (\lambda + \delta)^2 + \delta k^*(\lambda + \delta) / (\lambda + \delta) \\ m_{23} &= \lambda(1 - h^*(\gamma + \lambda)) / (\gamma + \lambda)^2 + \lambda h^*(\gamma + \lambda) / (\gamma + \lambda) \\ m_{24} &= \gamma(1 - h^*(\gamma + \lambda)) / (\gamma + \lambda)^2 + \lambda h^*(\gamma + \lambda) / (\gamma + \lambda) \\ m_{42} &= -k^*(\lambda + \delta) \end{aligned}$$

It can be easily verified that

$$\begin{aligned} m_{01} + m_{02} &= \mu_0 & m_{10} + m_{13} &= \mu_1 \\ m_{20} + m_{23} + m_{24} &= \mu_2 & m_{31} + m_{32} + m_{35} &= \mu_3 \\ m_{42} + m_{45} + m_{46} &= \mu_4 \end{aligned}$$

Mean Time to System Failure

The mean time to system failure is given by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_0(t) &= q_{01}(t) \otimes \Omega_1(t) + q_{02}(t) \otimes \Omega_2(t) \\ \Omega_1(t) &= q_{10}(t) \otimes \Omega_0(t) + q_{13}(t) \otimes \Omega_3(t) \\ \Omega_2(t) &= q_{20}(t) \otimes \Omega_0(t) + q_{23}(t) \otimes \Omega_3(t) + q_{24}(t) \otimes \Omega_4(t) \\ \Omega_3(t) &= q_{31}(t) \otimes \Omega_1(t) + q_{32}(t) \otimes \Omega_2(t) + q_{35}(t) \\ \Omega_4(t) &= q_{42}(t) \otimes \Omega_2(t) + q_{45}(t) + q_{46}(t) \end{aligned}$$

Solving above equation by taking Laplace Stieltjes transformations and solving for $\Omega_0^{**}(s)$, we get

$$\Omega_0^{**}(s) = \frac{N(s)}{D(s)}$$

Where

$$N(s) = q_{35}[q_{01}q_{13}(q_{24}q_{42}-1) - q_{02}q_{23}] - (q_{45}+q_{46}) [q_{13}q_{24} (q_{01}q_{32} - q_{02}q_{31})+q_{02}q_{24}]$$

$$D(s) = -1+q_{24}q_{42} - q_{13}q_{31}q_{24}q_{42} - q_{01}q_{10}q_{24}q_{42} + q_{23}q_{32} + q_{13}q_{31} + q_{01}q_{10} -$$

$$q_{01}q_{10}q_{23}q_{32} + q_{01}q_{13}q_{20}q_{32} + q_{02}q_{10}q_{31}q_{23} + q_{20}q_{02} - q_{20}q_{02}q_{13}q_{31}$$

$$MTSF = \Omega_0 = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} [(1-\Omega_0^{**}(s))/s] = \{D'(0)-N'(0)\}/D(0)$$

Where

$$D'(0) - N'(0) = m_{24} [p_{10}p_{01}p_{42} + p_{13}p_{31}p_{42} - p_{42}] + p_{24} [m_{13}p_{31}p_{42} + p_{13}p_{31}m_{42} + p_{13}p_{31}m_{42} +$$

$$m_{01}p_{10}p_{42} + p_{01}m_{10}p_{42} + p_{01}m_{10}m_{42} - m_{42}] - m_{23}p_{32} - p_{23}m_{32} - m_{13}p_{31} - p_{13}m_{31} - m_{01}p_{10}(1-$$

$$p_{23}p_{32}) + p_{01}p_{10}(p_{23}p_{32}-1) + p_{01}p_{10}(m_{23}p_{32} + p_{23}m_{32}) - [m_{01}p_{13}p_{20}p_{32} + p_{01}m_{13}p_{20}p_{32} + p_{01}$$

$$p_{13}m_{20}p_{32}] + p_{01}m_{13}p_{20}p_{32} + m_{02}p_{10}p_{31}p_{23} + p_{02}m_{10}p_{31}p_{23} + p_{02}m_{10}m_{31}p_{23} + p_{01}p_{10}p_{31}m_{23}$$

$$+ m_{20}p_{02}(1-p_{13}p_{31}) - p_{20}m_{02}(1-p_{13}p_{31}) + p_{20}p_{02}(m_{13}p_{31} - p_{13}m_{31}) - m_{35} [p_{01}p_{13}(p_{24}p_{42}-1)] -$$

$$p_{35}(m_{01}p_{13} + p_{01}m_{13})(p_{24}p_{42}-1) + p_{01}p_{13}(m_{24}p_{42} + p_{24}m_{42}) - m_{02}p_{23} - p_{02}m_{23} + (\mu_0 - m_{42})[p_{13}$$

$$p_{24}(p_{01}p_{32} - p_{02}p_{31}) + p_{02}p_{24}(1-p_{42})[m_{13}p_{24} + p_{13}m_{24}](p_{01}p_{32} - p_{02}p_{31}) + p_{13}p_{24}(m_{01}p_{32}$$

$$+ p_{01}p_{32} - m_{02}p_{31} - p_{02}m_{31}) + m_{02}p_{24} + p_{02}m_{24}]$$

$$D(0) = p_{35} [-p_{01}p_{13}(1-p_{24}p_{42}) - p_{02}p_{23}] - (p_{45}+p_{46}) [p_{01}p_{13}p_{32}p_{24} + p_{02}p_{24} - p_{02}p_{13}p_{13}p_{24}]$$

Availability of the system

The point wise availability $\mathbb{A}V_i(t)$ of the system is given by

$$\mathbb{A}V_0(t) = \dot{M}_0(t) + q_{01}(t) \odot \mathbb{A}V_1(t) + q_{02} \odot \mathbb{A}V_2(t)$$

$$\mathbb{A}V_1(t) = \dot{M}_1(t) + q_{10}(t) \odot \mathbb{A}V_0(t) + q_{13} \odot \mathbb{A}V_3(t)$$

$$\mathbb{A}V_2(t) = \dot{M}_2(t) + q_{20}(t) \odot \mathbb{A}V_0(t) + q_{23} \odot \mathbb{A}V_3(t) + q_{24} \odot \mathbb{A}V_4(t)$$

$$\mathbb{A}V_3(t) = \dot{M}_3(t) + q_{31}(t) \odot \mathbb{A}V_1(t) + q_{32}(t) \odot \mathbb{A}V_2(t) + q_{33}^{(5)} \odot \mathbb{A}V_3(t)$$

$$\mathbb{A}V_4(t) = \dot{M}_4(t) + q_{42}(t) \odot \mathbb{A}V_2(t) + q_{43}^{(6)} \odot \mathbb{A}V_4(t)$$

Now taking Laplace transform of these equations and solving them for $\mathbb{A}V_0^*(s)$, we get

$$\mathbb{A}V_0^*(s) = \frac{N_1(s)}{D_1(s)}$$

The steady states availability is given by

$$\mathbb{A}V_0^{**} = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} (s\mathbb{A}V_0^*(s)) = \frac{N_1^{(0)}}{D_1^{(0)}}$$

Where

$$\dot{M}_0(t) = \mu_0$$

$$\dot{M}_1(t) = \mu_1$$

$$\dot{M}_2(t) = \mu_2$$

$$\dot{M}_3(t) = \mu_3$$

$$\dot{M}_4(t) = \mu_4$$

$$N_1(0) = (p_{24}p_{42}\mu_0 - p_{24}p_{02})(1 - p_{33}^{(5)} - p_{13}p_{31}) - p_{01}p_{13}p_{24}[p_{32}\mu_4 + \mu_3(t)] +$$

$$(p_{24}p_{42}p_{01}\mu_1 + p_{02}\mu_2)(1 - p_{33}^{(5)}) + (p_{01}\mu_1 - \mu_0)(-1 - p_{43}^{(6)})(-1 - p_{33}^{(5)}) + p_{23}p_{32}$$

$$- \mu_0p_{13}p_{31} + p_{13}p_{01}(-p_{32}\mu_2 - \mu_3) + p_{02}p_{23}\mu_3 - p_{02}p_{31}(-p_{23}\mu_1 + p_{13}\mu_2)$$

And

$$D_1(0)=0$$

$$D_1'(0) = m_{24} [p_{42} (1-p_{35})(-1+p_{01}) - p_{13} p_{31}p_{23}p_{42}] + p_{24} [m_{42} (1-p_{35})(-1+p_{01}) + m_{35}p_{42} (-1+p_{01}) + m_{01} p_{42} (1-p_{35}) + m_{13}p_{31} p_{42} + m_{31}p_{13}p_{42} + m_{42}p_{13}p_{31}] - m_{46} [(-1+ p_{35})(1+p_{01}p_{10} + p_{02}p_{20}) + p_{23}p_{32} (1-p_{01}p_{10}) - p_{13}p_{31} (1-p_{02}p_{20}) - p_{01}p_{13}p_{20}p_{32} - p_{02}p_{10} p_{31}p_{23}] - p_{46} [m_{35}(1+p_{01}p_{10}+p_{02}p_{20})(-1+p_{35})(m_{10} p_{10} + m_{10}p_{01} - m_{01} p_{20} + m_{20}p_{02}) + m_{23} p_{23} (1-p_{01}p_{10}) + m_{32}p_{23} (1-p_{01} p_{10}) - p_{23}p_{32} (m_{01}p_{10} + m_{10}p_{01} - m_{13}p_{31} (1- p_{02}p_{20}) - m_{31}p_{13} (1-p_{02}p_{20}) - p_{13}p_{31} (-m_{02}p_{20} - m_{20}p_{02}) - m_{01} p_{13}p_{20}p_{32} - m_{13}p_{01}p_{20}p_{32} - m_{20} p_{01} p_{13}p_{32} - m_{32}p_{01}p_{13} p_{20} + m_{02} p_{10}p_{13}p_{23} - m_{10}p_{02}p_{31} p_{23} - m_{31}p_{02}p_{10}p_{23} - m_{23}p_{02}p_{10}p_{31}]$$

Busy Period Analysis of Repair man:

Let $BP_i(t)$ be the probability that the server is busy at an instant t given that the system entered regenerative state i at $t = 0$. The following are the recursive relations for $B_i(t)$:

$$BP_0(t) = q_{01}(t) \odot BP_1(t) + q_{02}(t) \odot BP_2(t)$$

$$BP_1(t) = W_1 + q_{10}(t) \odot BP_0(t) + q_{13}(t) \odot BP_3(t)$$

$$BP_2(t) = W_2(t) + q_{20}(t) \odot BP_0(t) + q_{23}(t) \odot BP_3(t) + q_{24}(t) \odot BP_4(t)$$

$$BP_3(t) = W_3(t) + q_{31}(t) \odot BP_1(t) + q_{32}(t) \odot BP_2(t) + q_{35}(t) \odot BP_3(t)$$

$$BP_4(t) = W_4(t) + q_{42}(t) \odot BP_2(t) + q_{44}(t) \odot BP_4(t)$$

Taking Laplace transform of the equations of busy period analysis and solving them for $BP_0^*(s)$, we get

$$BP_0^*(s) = \frac{N_2(s)}{D_1(s)}$$

In the steady state

$$BP_0 = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} sB^*(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{sN_2(s)}{D_1(s)} = \frac{N_2(0)}{D_1'(0)}$$

here

$$N_2(0) = (1-P_{46}) [W_1 p_{01} (1-p_{35}) + p_{01} W_1 p_{23}p_{32} - W_2 p_{32} - W_3 p_{02} W_2 (1- p_{35} - p_{13}p_{31}) + p_{02}p_{23} (W_1p_{31} + W_3)] + (1-p_{35}) [p_{01} W_1 p_{45} p_{24} - p_{02}W_4p_{24}] + p_{01}p_{13} p_{24} (W_3 p_{42} - W_4 p_{32}) - p_{02}p_{13}p_{23}p_{31}$$

$D_1'(0)$ is already defined

Expected Number of Inspection by the Repairman:

Let $R_i(t)$ be the probability that the server is busy at an instant t given that the system entered regenerative state i at $t = 0$. The following are the recursive relations for $R_i(t)$:

$$R_0(t) = q_{01}(t) \odot R_1(t) + q_{02}(t) \odot R_2(t)$$

$$R_1(t) = K_1 + q_{10}(t) \odot R_0(t) + q_{13}(t) \odot R_3(t)$$

$$R_2(t) = K_2(t) + q_{20}(t) \odot R_0(t) + q_{23}(t) \odot R_3(t) + q_{24}(t) \odot R_4(t)$$

$$R_3(t) = q_{31}(t) \odot R_1(t) + q_{32}(t) \odot R_2(t) + q_{35}(t) \odot R_3(t)$$

$$R_4(t) = q_{42}(t) \odot R_2(t) + q_{46}(t) \odot R_4(t)$$

Taking Laplace transform of the equations of busy period analysis and solving them for $R_0^*(s)$, we get

$$R_0^*(s) = \frac{N_2(s)}{D_1(s)}$$

In the steady state

$$R_0 = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} sB^*(s) = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{sN_2(s)}{D_1(s)} = \frac{N_2(0)}{D_1'(0)}$$

here

$$N_2(0) = (-1+P_{46}) [K_1 p_{01} (1-p_{35} -p_{23}p_{32}) + K_2 p_{01}p_{13} p_{32} + p_{02} K_1 p_{31} p_{23} - K_2 (1-p_{35} -p_{31}p_{13})]$$

$D_1'(0)$ is already defined

Particular cases:

If we take repair rate and inspection time as negative binomial distributions as

$$h(t) = \rho e^{-\rho t} \quad k(t) = \xi e^{-\xi t}$$

Then we get,

$$p_{01} = \lambda/(\lambda+\alpha)$$

$$p_{10} = \beta/(\alpha+\beta)$$

$$p_{20} = \rho/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)$$

$$p_{24} = \gamma/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)$$

$$p_{32} = \beta/(\gamma+\beta+\rho)$$

$$p_{42} = \xi/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)$$

$$p_{46} = \delta/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)$$

$$p_{54} = 1$$

$$\mu_0 = 1/(\lambda+\alpha)$$

$$\mu_2 = 1/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)$$

$$\mu_4 = 1/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)$$

$$m_{01} = \lambda/(\lambda+\alpha)^2$$

$$m_{10} = \beta/(\alpha+\beta)^2$$

$$m_{20} = \rho/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)^2$$

$$m_{24} = \gamma/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)^2$$

$$m_{32} = \beta/(\beta+\gamma+\rho)^2$$

$$m_{42} = \xi/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)^2$$

$$m_{46} = \delta/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)^2$$

$$m_{54} = 1$$

$$p_{02} = \alpha/(\lambda+\alpha)$$

$$p_{13} = \alpha/(\alpha+\beta)$$

$$p_{23} = \lambda/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)$$

$$p_{31} = \rho/(\gamma+\beta+\rho)$$

$$p_{35} = \gamma/(\gamma+\beta+\rho)$$

$$p_{45} = \lambda/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)$$

$$p_{53} = 1$$

$$p_{64} = 1$$

$$\mu_1 = 1/(\alpha+\beta)$$

$$\mu_3 = 1/(\gamma+\beta+\rho)$$

$$m_{02} = \alpha/(\lambda+\alpha)^2$$

$$m_{13} = \alpha/(\alpha+\beta)^2$$

$$m_{23} = \lambda/(\gamma+\lambda+\rho)^2$$

$$m_{31} = \rho/(\gamma+\beta+\rho)^2$$

$$m_{35} = \gamma/(\gamma+\beta+\rho)^2$$

$$m_{45} = \lambda/(\lambda+\delta+\xi)^2$$

$$m_{53} = 1$$

$$m_{64} = 1$$

Conclusion

On the bases on the above particular cases the expected outcomes shows that the optimum value of the system parameters management may control the units repair and failure rates depending upon the availability of finances and market circumstances.

State Transition Diagram

$S_0=(P,Q,R,S)$	$S_3=(P_r,Q_r,R,S)$
$S_1=(P_r,Q,R,S)$	$S_4=(P,Q_r,R_r,S)$
$S_2=(P,Q_r,R,S)$	$S_5=(P_r,Q_r,R_r,S)$
$S_6=(P,Q_r,R_r,S_r)$	

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